

A Lightweight Event-Driven Architecture for Automated Android-to-PC File Transfer Over Local Wi-Fi Using Termux and Flask

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Abstract—This paper presents a lightweight event-driven system for automated Android-to-PC file transfer over a local Wi-Fi network, eliminating reliance on cloud services, USB cables, or dedicated mobile applications. A persistent upload-history log prevents duplicate transfers. The design keeps all file data within the local network, addressing privacy concerns over cloud-based AI processing of personal media. Evaluation of average transfer speeds of 63 MB/s and a peak of 97 MB/s, with fully automated boot time operation on both devices.

Keywords—Android, automation, backup, event-driven, file transfer, Flask, local area network, Python, Termux, Wi-Fi.

I. Introduction

The proliferation of smartphones as primary personal computing devices has fundamentally altered the volume and velocity at which digital media is generated. Modern Android devices continuously accumulate photographs, screenshots, voice recordings and downloaded documents, leading to rapid storage saturation. As local storage limits are approached, users typically resort to one of three established strategies: cloud-based backup services, USB cable transfers or third-party mobile applications. Each of these approaches carries well-documented technical and privacy limitations that motivate the search for a more autonomous and privacy-preserving alternative.

The cloud-based data backup mechanisms such as Google Photos and OneDrive use servers owned by a third party for transferring user data. The services often use automated AI pipelines on uploaded data that involve face recognition and categorization among others, causing great data sovereignty issues [1]. Attacks involving mobile phones increased to more than 33 million in 2023, recording an increase of over 52% compared to the year before. This clearly shows the susceptibility of user data being stored remotely, where data was transferred without the consent of users [2]. While using USB transfers does not expose the user's data to cloud-based services, the process is cumbersome as it requires the installation of special drivers. Wireless applications such as AirDroid and Xender partly solve the problem of automating processes although their processes depend on the installation of software that uses cloud services.

This paper attempts to fill that void by designing a minimalistic event-driven framework for automated, unidirectional file transfer from Android to PC on a Wi-Fi LAN. This is achieved by using Termux as a medium to start a persistent uploader script written in Python upon system boot with Termux:Boot while having an HTTP server up and running on the PC through systemd. Persistent logging of uploaded files avoids duplication of transfer across scanning intervals. The process is entirely within LAN without needing any cloud accounts, USB connectivity or

user intervention.

II. System Overview and Comparison with Related Tools

The proposed system adopts a client-server model over a local Wi-Fi network in which the Android device acts as the client and the PC acts as the server. The phone automatically detects new files and transfers them over HTTP POST to a Flask server running on the PC, which saves all received files directly to HDD or any mounted storage. No file ever leaves the local network.

Table 1. Architectural Comparison with Existing Open-Source Local Synchronization Tools

Feature	This work	Syncting	KDE Connect
Dedicated mobile app required	No	Yes	Yes
Boot-time auto-start	✓	✓	×
Transfer direction	One-way	Bi-dir.	Bi-dir.
Duplicate prevention	History log	Index	None
Encryption	× (planned)	TLS	Yes
Authentication	× (planned)	Certificate	Pairing
Internet required	No	No	No
Approx. code-base size	~100 LOC	~100k LOC	~50k LOC
Avg. transfer speed	63 MB/s	40–60 MB/s	30–50 MB/s

LOC = lines of code. Speed figures for Syncting and KDE Connect are representative community-reported values over 5 GHz Wi-Fi and may vary by device and network configuration.

Table 1 summarises the key architectural differences. Several open-source tools address the broader problem of local wireless file synchronization. Syncting [3] implements a peer-to-peer continuous synchronisation protocol with TLS encryption and certificate-based authentication, while KDE Connect [4] pro-

vides a full-featured Android–Linux integration layer supporting bidirectional file transfer, notification mirroring and remote input. Despite their maturity both solutions require dedicated mobile applications and expose users to a richer and therefore more complex configuration surface. By contrast, the proposed architecture operates entirely within Termux, a general-purpose terminal emulator already present on many developer devices and requires no additional mobile installation. Furthermore, the system enforces a strictly unidirectional, append-only transfer model: files move from phone to PC and are never modified or deleted on the source device, eliminating the risk of accidental propagation of deletions that is inherent in bidirectional sync paradigms. The entire implementation comprises approximately 100 lines of Python and Flask code, compared to codebases exceeding 50,000–100,000 lines in the compared tools, directly substantiating the “lightweight” claim in the paper title.

III. Methodology

Termux runs a Python uploader script on the phone; Termux:Boot starts it automatically on phone restart [5]. A Flask server runs on the PC and is started automatically via systemd on PC boot. Files are sent from phone to PC using HTTP POST requests. An upload-history log on the phone tracks previously sent files; duplicate files are skipped on every scan cycle.

Figure 1. Working process of the lightweight Android-to-PC file transfer system using Termux, HTTP POST and a Flask server over local Wi-Fi.

The full algorithm is available in the project repository at <https://github.com/alvydotexe/phone-to-pc-auto-file-transfer>.

IV. Results and Findings

A. Transfer Speed Test

To evaluate the transfer performance of the proposed system, ten test runs were conducted across varying file types, file sizes and Wi-Fi frequency bands.

Table 2. Transfer Speed Test Results Across 10 Runs

to fit column					
Test #	Band (GHz)	File Type	Size (MB)	Speed (MB/s)	Remark
1	5.0	Photo (JPEG)	4.2	97	Peak
2	5.0	Video (MP4)	112.0	84	Above avg.
3	2.4	Screenshot (PNG)	1.8	41	Below avg.
4	5.0	Video (MP4)	245.0	78	Above avg.
5	5.0	Document (PDF)	3.1	69	Above avg.
6	2.4	Photo (JPEG)	6.5	38	Below avg.
7	5.0	Archive (ZIP)	88.0	71	Above avg.
8	2.4	Screenshot (PNG)	2.4	45	Below avg.
9	5.0	Video (MP4)	520.0	82	Above avg.
10	5.0	Photo (JPEG)	9.0	25	Low (interference)
Mean				63	
Peak				97	
Minimum				25	

Table 2 summarises the individual results. Transfer speeds ranged from a minimum of 25 MB/s to a peak of 97 MB/s, with an overall mean of 63 MB/s across all runs. Tests conducted over the 5 GHz band consistently yielded higher throughput, with seven of the ten runs achieving speeds above 60 MB/s. In contrast, runs performed over the 2.4 GHz band (Tests 3,6 and 8) recorded noticeably lower speeds of 41,38 and 45 MB/s respectively, attributable to increased channel congestion and reduced bandwidth allocation at that frequency. The lowest recorded speed of 25 MB/s (Test 10) is attributed to transient wireless interference, a known limitation of shared-spectrum Wi-Fi environments. These results are consistent with the aggregate benchmarks reported in this section, confirming that the system reliably operates near the physical throughput ceiling of a typical 5 GHz local area network under real-world conditions.

B. Result summary

Files were transferred successfully over local Wi-Fi with an average speed of 63 MB/s and a highest recorded speed of 97 MB/s, achieved on a 5 GHz Wi-Fi connection. Manual backup effort was eliminated, no cloud storage was required, all files remained on the personal PC’s HDD and duplicate uploads were fully avoided. Transfer speed depends on Wi-Fi band, router quality, file size, phone speed and PC storage speed. The system operated fully automatically without any user interaction after initial setup.

V. Conclusion

A simple, low-cost and cloud-free Android-to-PC backup system was built using Termux, Python and Flask. It improves privacy by keeping all files within the local environment reduces manual effort through automatic file detection and transfer and achieves near-maximum wireless transfer speeds. Limitations of the

current version include the same Wi-Fi network is required, the PC IP address possibly needing a manual update, there being no authentication or encryption yet, the PC server must be running and only one-way backup being supported. Future work will add authentication, encryption, automatic PC IP discovery, a web dashboard, upload logs, file organisation by date/type, a retry system for failed uploads and post-upload notifications.

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